

Seeking for dependencies of the high frequency “kappa” parameter of earthquake spectrum on weather/climate conditions

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Abstract

We investigate the seasonal variability of the κ_0 parameter, which describes the near-surface high-frequency attenuation of seismic waves. We analyze data from the ARGONET vertical array of accelerometers in Cephalonia, Greece, focusing on comparisons of high-frequency spectral decay between the surface station CK0 and the borehole bedrock station CK83. The study uses the ARGONET database records from July 2015 to October 2022. Results using two different approaches agree on a significant variation of κ_0 at CK0, with lower values in summer (dry period for Cephalonia) and higher values in winter (rainy period). This suggests that weather/climate related factors, such as soil moisture and temperature, influence near-surface attenuation, at least as expressed through the value of κ_0 . This result challenges the assumption of a static value for κ_0 often made in site characterization for seismic hazard assessment.

Background

Kappa, κ , is used to quantify the attenuation of high-frequency seismic waves as they travel through the Earth's crust and near-surface materials. First introduced by Anderson and Hough (1984), it is determined from the slope of the high-frequency decay in the Fourier Amplitude Spectrum (FAS) of acceleration, typically using earthquake ground motion records. It is often analyzed in one component that reflects the attenuation occurring along the seismic ray path due to anelastic and scattering processes in the crust and one that quantifies the near-surface attenuation due to the shallow geological conditions, particularly in sedimentary layers.

The component of κ related to site-specific near-surface attenuation, widely called the kappa-zero, κ_0 , is a crucial parameter in engineering seismology (e.g., Boore and Joyner, 1997; Ktenidou et al., 2014; Douglas et al., 2020). It enhances the accuracy of ground motion models in predicting high-frequency spectral amplitudes and is directly utilized in developing design spectra and ground motion simulations. By incorporating κ_0 , engineers can better estimate seismic demands on structures, especially those sensitive to high-frequency vibrations. That is why it has been considered vital for critical facilities, such as nuclear power plants, where accurate characterization of high-frequency ground motion components is essential.

While κ has been widely adopted by both the seismological and civil engineering communities, several challenges and criticisms have emerged regarding its application. Estimating κ involves subjective decisions, such as selecting the frequency range for analysis and assuming linearity in the spectral decay. This can lead to variability and inconsistencies, which are further amplified by a lack of standardized methodologies in the parameter's computation and data with insufficient high-frequency content (e.g., Ktenidou et al., 2014). Furthermore, κ reflects a combination of attenuation processes, including scattering, anelastic absorption, site amplification effects and even soil-structure interaction and similar effects emerging from sensor installation practices (e.g., Parolai and Bindi, 2004; Hollender et al., 2020). Disentangling these contributions can be difficult and complicates the interpretation of the parameter under discussion. Another recently proposed process that may affect the spectral region where κ is measured is soil-atmosphere interaction, which suggests a seasonal variation in κ (e.g., Roumelioti et al., 2020; Grendas et al., 2025).

Objectives

This study aims to investigate the seasonal variability of κ_0 using data from the ARGONET vertical array, a special infrastructure for site effect studies on Cephalonia Island, Greece. The objective is to use this well-studied site to extract valuable insights about the possible contribution of weather/climate into the complex nature of near-surface, high-frequency attenuation.

Data and Initial Processing

The ARGONET infrastructure includes, among other components, a vertical array of accelerometers located in the sedimentary valley of Koutavos, south-southeast of Argostoli, the capital of the island of Cephalonia in western Greece. Details of the infrastructure can be found in Theodoulidis et al. (2018). In this study, we only use data from the surface and deepest sensor of the vertical array, code-named CK0 and CK83, respectively. CK0 is installed inside a light wooden construction on a relatively soft site. Average shear-wave velocity, V_s , for the upper 30 m depth (VS_{30}) according to the V_s values from different methods (cross-hole, down-hole, seismic interferometry) reported in Cushing et al., (2020), is in the range 201-262 m/s. CK83, on the other hand, installed at a depth of 83 m, is reported to be in the limestone bedrock (Theodoulidis et al., 2018). For the purposes of this study, this station is used as a “reference” station, both in the classical sense of engineering seismology (i.e., absence of

significant site effects), but also in the sense that it is very unlikely to be significantly affected by short-term ground-atmosphere interactions (Roumelioti et al., 2020; Grendas et al., 2025).

Since its launch in 2015, ARGONET has been in continuous recording mode. Earthquake records that include CK83 acceleration time histories with a Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) $\geq 2\text{mg}$ are processed and organized in the ARGONET database, which is openly available online (https://argonet-kefalonia.org/data/argonet_data/). In this work, we process the horizontal records at CK0 and CK83 stations of 964 earthquakes epicentered in the wider area of Western Greece and occurring from July 2015 to October 2022.

The horizontal acceleration waveforms were first processed for standard corrections and S-wave window selection. The various steps of this processing are not presented here for reasons of space, but are described in detail in Grendas et al. (2021). Briefly, we selected S-wave windows of variable duration, depending on the earthquake-receiver distance and the earthquake magnitude. These S-wave windows were Fast Fourier Transformed (FFT) and smoothed following Konno and Ohmachi (1998) (with the parameter b of the method set to 50). Spectra were first generated for each horizontal component separately, and then combined (square root of the sum of squares) to compute a single horizontal spectrum per station and earthquake.

Computation of κ and κ_0

Kappa values were computed for each horizontal FAS, $A(f)$, based on a linear fit of its amplitudes in the high-frequency spectral region in between user-defined frequencies f_e and f_{end} , following the original work of Anderson and Hough (1984) and the equation:

$$A(f) = A_0 \exp(-\pi \kappa f) \quad (f > f_e) \quad [1]$$

in which A_0 corresponds to the plateau of spectral amplitudes at $f < f_e$. Figure 1 shows the computation of κ schematically. In addition to the examined earthquake spectrum (in blue), the corresponding Fourier spectrum of a noise window preceding the earthquake signal is shown (in red). The part of the earthquake spectrum used in the analysis is required to be above a certain multiple of the noise spectrum. Figure 1 shows an example of a multiple of 3. In this work, we set a stricter minimum signal-to-noise level of 5.

Figure 1. The Fourier Amplitude Spectra (FAS) of the S-wave earthquake motion (light blue line), its smoothed version (bold blue line), and the corresponding smoothed FAS of the noise before the arrival of the P-wave (bold red line). The red dashed line marks the 3-fold noise FAS level as an example of the minimum threshold for the earthquake signal to be considered reliable (Signal-to-Noise Ratio, SNR ≥ 3). Black lines show the least-squares regression of $\log(\text{FAS})$ values in the frequency range from f_e to f_{end} , ± 1 standard deviation (STD) of the mean.

We computed κ values for four different fixed frequency ranges, i.e., 6-25 Hz, 6-35 Hz, 10-25 Hz, and 10-35 Hz. The results for each of the two stations and each frequency range studied are plotted against epicentral distance in Figure 2. By linear regression of the distributions in Figure 2, it is possible to separate the “path” and the epicentral distance independent (“site” or/and “source” considered) terms of kappa. The mean values for the second term of kappa or κ_0 , i.e., the values of κ corresponding to zero epicentral distance are reported in Figure 2 and Table 1. We restricted the linear regressions to data corresponding to epicentral distances ≤ 60 km, partly because data points were sparse at larger distances and partly because around 60 km there is an obvious change in the regional attenuation that could not be fit by a single line. We also kept the slope of the linear fit, based on the regression of the entire set of ARGONET data (i.e., all stations of the vertical array, not shown in this paper), fixed so as to reasonably assume exactly the same path attenuation factor for the two stations studied, since they are both located at the same epicentral distance.

Results in both Figure 2 and Table 1 show a larger variability of κ values at CK0 compared to CK83. They also highlight that mean κ_0 values are, as expected, larger at the “soft” CK0 stations and much smaller in the “soft rock” CK83 station. Another rather expected result is the dependence of κ and consequently of the κ_0 values on the frequency range used in the analysis, further highlighting the problem in understanding κ in the absence of standardized analysis practices.

Computation of $\Delta\kappa_0$

The exclusive site-specific character of κ_0 has been a subject of debate (e.g., Ktenidou et al., 2014 and references therein). Most studies support it (e.g., Cotton et al., 2006; Drouet et al., 2010; Ktenidou et al., 2013; Ktenidou et al., 2015). However, others also argue for a dependence on the seismic source (e.g., Tsai and Chen, 2000; Purvance and Anderson, 2003; Kilb et al., 2012), a component that would be difficult to isolate based on classical linear regression analysis on the κ measurements of a single site. To overcome this difficulty and secure that we have effectively removed any possible source effects, instead of using κ or κ_0 we used one site as target and one as reference and we computed their κ differences, $\Delta\kappa$. $\Delta\kappa$ is equivalent to $\Delta\kappa_0$ under the realistic assumption that the wavefield at both examined stations experiences the same along-path attenuation.

Figure 2. κ values computed from the earthquake records at stations CK0 (left) and CK83(right) considering four different frequency ranges (noted on top left of each subplot). The slope of the linear regression has been kept constant considering all ARGONET data. Mean κ_0 values (κ at zero distance) and the ± 1 STD are also noted in each subplot.

Table 1. Computed κ_0 and $\Delta\kappa_0$ mean values and their standard deviations (σ) for four examined frequency ranges. $\Delta\kappa_0$ results are shown for both applied methods described in the text. Columns named “SV model range” list the quantity “maximum seasonal model amplitude - minimum seasonal model amplitude” for each examined case.

$f_e - f_{end}$ (Hz)	CK0		CK83		$\Delta\kappa_0$ Method1			$\Delta\kappa_0$ Method2		
	κ_0 (ms)	$\sigma\kappa_0$ κ_0 (ms)	κ_0 (ms)	$\sigma\kappa_0$ κ_0 (ms)	$\Delta\kappa_0$ (ms)	$\sigma\Delta\kappa_0$ $\Delta\kappa_0$ (ms)	SV model range	$\Delta\kappa_0$ (ms)	$\sigma\Delta\kappa_0$ $\Delta\kappa_0$ (ms)	Sv model range
6-25	19.7	11.4	6.0	8.9	18	6	7	17.4	0.8	6.5
6-35	18.6	8.0	7.2	6.8	14	6	5	14.4	0.5	4.3
10-25	26.2	12.9	8.0	10.7	20	10	10	20.6	1.1	9.6
10-35	20.7	8.1	9.1	6.9	15	10	6	14.4	0.7	4.5

In our case, CK0 is the target site and we examine its high-frequency shaking characteristics with respect to the borehole station CK83 using two different methods: In “Method 1”, we used pairs of κ values from CK0 and CK83 stations to estimate $\Delta\kappa = \kappa_{(CK0)} - \kappa_{(CK83)}$ and equivalently $\Delta\kappa_0$. In “Method 2”, we measured $\Delta\kappa_0$ directly on Standard Spectral Ratios (SSRs) of CK0 with respect to CK83. The two approaches will be presented in more detail in the following.

The computation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ from the κ values of CK0 and CK83 is straightforward and resulting values are plotted in Figures 3a and 4. For examining possible variations of $\Delta\kappa_0$ with seasons (Seasonal Variation, SV), we considered a “pseudo-waveform” $\Delta\kappa_0(\text{day})$, where “day” is derived from date considering as starting point the 1st of January of each year. We analyzed this pseudo-waveform for its frequency content via FFT. We computed FAS only for periods T_{SV}^h , corresponding to 365/h for h=1 and h=2, seeking for possible variations with a return period of the order of a year or half a year and aiming to a smooth model of the phenomenon, if proven significant. The seasonal variation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ ($\Delta\kappa_h(SV)$), was finally modeled as the sum of the 2,

discrete period (T_{SV}^h) cosine wavelets, based on the corresponding scaled FAS Amplitude, $Y(T_{SV}^h)$, and adopted phase, $\varphi(T_{SV}^h)$ (in degrees), as in:

$$\Delta\kappa_h(SV) = Y(T_{SV}^h) \cdot \cos\left\{\left(2 \cdot \pi / T_{SV}^h\right) \cdot [\text{Date} - \varphi(T_{SV}^h)]\right\} \quad [2]$$

Figure 3a shows as an example the starting data and resulting model (red dots and cyan lines in Figure 3a) for the frequency range 6-25Hz and the corresponding result of the FFT analysis (Figure 3b). The starting data and final models for the seasonal variation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ for all four tested frequency ranges are presented in Figure 4. If there is a time pattern in $\Delta\kappa_0$, a clear peak is expected to be observed in plots like the example plot in Figure 3b. In the specific example of Figure 3b, a prominent peak is seen at the examined period of 1 year, suggesting a yearly repeating change in $\Delta\kappa_0$.

In general, Figure 3 shows a clear time variation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ measurements, with lower $\Delta\kappa_0$ during summer and highest during winter. The proposed model for this variation also predicts the lowest $\Delta\kappa_0$ values during the first third of July and the highest values during the first third of January of each year. These results were consistent for all four examined frequency ranges and any differences were restricted to the order of a few days.

The modelled seasonal variation of the high-frequency ground motion amplitudes at CK0 with respect to those in CK83 can be characterized as significant, since its range (maximum seasonal model amplitude - minimum seasonal model amplitude) is of the order of 1 standard deviation of the mean $\Delta\kappa_0$ from data (Table 1, $\sigma_{\Delta\kappa_0} \Delta\kappa_0$, Columns 7, 8). This means that the proposed model, if used to “correct” the observed data examined in this study, could lower the variability in κ_0 or $\Delta\kappa_0$ measurements and lead to more robust computations of the mean κ_0 . The performance of the seasonal variation model of $\Delta\kappa_0$ shows some dependence on the frequency interval adopted in the analysis, but in all cases explains much of the variability of the examined parameter (Table 1).

Figure 3. Variation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ with date a) data points of individual $\Delta\kappa_0$ measurements for the frequency range 6-25Hz and superimposed model of the seasonal variation of $\Delta\kappa_0 \pm 1$ standard deviation (STD) of the mean model (cyan curves), b) Fourier Amplitude Spectrum (FAS) of the pseudo-waveform $\Delta\kappa_0(\text{day})$ considered. Shaded areas mark the areas of the investigated return periods of the phenomenon (i.e., at 1 year and 6 months). The difference between the lower and higher $\Delta\kappa_0$ values predicted by the proposed model are noted in the top left of a).

Figure 4. $\Delta\kappa_0$ values based on the κ_0 measurements at CK0 and CK83 stations ($\kappa_{(CK0)} - \kappa_{(CK83)}$) for the 4 examined frequency ranges. The modeled seasonal variation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ and its Standard Deviation (STD), are shown in cyan solid and dashed lines, respectively. The highest value of the seasonal $\Delta\kappa_0$ model is predicted to occur in July and the lowest in January of each year. The difference between the lowest and highest predicted $\Delta\kappa_0$, is written in the top left of each subplot.

The alternative approach to compute $\Delta\kappa_0$ (our “Method 2”) is to measure it directly on Standard Spectral Ratios (SSRs) of CK0 with respect to CK83. By dividing the FAS of CK0 to those of CK83 and considering that the interstation distance is much smaller compared to any epicentral distance in the examined dataset, we assume that source and path effects are effectively removed (Borcherdt, 1970), including the path-dependent component of κ . In the high-frequency part of the SSR, the spectral division mainly includes the division of the factors $\exp(-\pi\kappa_{(CK0)}f)/\exp(-\pi\kappa_{(CK83)}f)$. The path-dependent component of κ is considered the same for both the surface and borehole station and is eliminated and what remains is the difference $\kappa_{0(CK0)} - \kappa_{0(CK83)}$, i.e., the quantity under study.

SSRs for the horizontal component of the ARGONET dataset have already been computed by Grendas et al. (2025). Herein, we use these published seasonal varying ratios to perform linear regression on their high-frequency parts and more specifically within the same four frequency ranges examined earlier (“Method 2”). The resulting $\Delta\kappa_0$ values are depicted in Figure 5, along with SSRs colored according to the date of their occurrence. Warm colors correspond to dry, summer months and cold colors to winter months and it is evident that the differences in the high-frequency signal of CK0 with respect to CK83 increases during winter and diminishes during the summer.

Linear regressions to compute the mean $\Delta\kappa_0$ and its values during the identified “extreme” seasonal variation periods (i.e., July-August and January-February) have been performed directly on the SSRs of Figure 5. Pertinent results are shown in each subplot, considering the four examined frequency ranges. The linear fits for the two extreme seasonal variation periods are also shown. $\Delta\kappa_0$ values and their STDs are also listed in Table 1, under “Method 2”.

By comparing the linear fits in Figure 5, it becomes evident how the seasonal variation can largely affect the computation of $\Delta\kappa_0$ (and directly of κ and κ_0), at least at the specific site examined in this study. Datasets with a biased concentration of summer recordings would provide much larger values of κ_0 compared to non-biased or inversely biased datasets. The effect seems to be more significant when the examined frequency range terminates at frequencies largely affected by seasonal variations. In Figure 5, for example, the left subplots including analysis up to 25Hz present much larger discrepancies between the two “extremes” with respect to subplots to the right where the analysis is extended well beyond the frequency range mostly affected by seasonal variation. All these observations raise another “red flag” when the engineering and seismological communities face the necessity to harmonize κ measurements for comparisons.

Overall, the results of the two methods for computing $\Delta\kappa_0$ are similar and this is demonstrated by the comparison of values reported in Table 1.

Figure 5. Mean Standard Spectral Ratios (SSRs) (for the 1st day of each month) between CK0 and CK83 stations colored according to the date of occurrence of. Subplots differentiate in the frequency range used for the linear regression. Double lines mark the regression results for the two extreme $\Delta\kappa_0$ cases (summer vs winter). On the top right of each subplot, the mean $\Delta\kappa_0$ and $\Delta\kappa_0$ values corresponding to the two extremes of the modelled seasonal variation are noted.

Conclusions/Discussion

Despite its limitations, kappa remains a valuable parameter for understanding high-frequency attenuation and

conducting site-specific hazard analyses. Its practical utility has made it a significant parameter of engineering seismology, but ongoing research aims to refine its estimation techniques and improve its integration into seismic hazard models. By addressing its limitations and standardizing methodologies, the role of kappa in seismic hazard analysis can be further enhanced.

In this work we addressed an additional process that may add to the lumped character of this single-number descriptor of high-frequency attenuation, i.e., the soil-atmosphere interaction. We specifically examined if the high-frequency part of the earthquake spectrum, i.e., the part commonly used for the computation of kappa, changes with a seasonal periodicity. To do so, we comparatively examined kappa values at one surface and one borehole, bedrock station. Our results demonstrate that the difference in κ_0 values of the two examined stations exhibit considerable variability due to seasonal weather conditions, the frequency range used in the computation of the parameter, and potentially source processes. The pronounced seasonal variation observed at the surface soft soil site CK0 highlights the influence of rainfall-induced changes in ground humidity on near-surface attenuation. This finding challenges the common assumption of a static, site-specific κ_0 value and requests further research on the possible need to consider seasonal variability of high-frequency ground motion in seismic hazard assessments.

The frequency-dependent behavior of κ_0 , evident in the variations observed across different tested frequency ranges, suggests that attenuation slopes might not be uniform across the entire high-frequency spectrum at a given site. This observation warrants further investigation to understand the underlying mechanisms driving these frequency-specific variations. It also adds to previous discussions in the published literature about the need to standardize the methods for computing kappa to be able to compare kappa values from different regions and studies and limit its broader applicability in seismic hazard models (e.g., Ktenidou et al., 2014).

This study also confirms the effectiveness of using SSR(f) for more robust κ_0 estimation, providing lower standard deviations compared to traditional methods based on individual kappa factor differences.

Overall, this research provides additional insights into the complex nature of κ_0 and its potential variability. Further research is needed to investigate seasonal variations of kappa at a statistically significant number of sites, quantify dependencies and develop improved predictive models that incorporate these sources of variability for enhanced accuracy and reliability.

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